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Inducing ferroptosis via nanomaterials: a novel and effective route in cancer therapy

Mine Ensoy¹, Berfin Ilayda Ozturk², Demet Cansaran-Duman^{1,*} and Açelya Yilmazer^{2,3,*} ¹ Biotechnology Institute, Ankara University, Keçiören, Ankara, Turkey² Department of Biomedical Engineering, Ankara University, Golbasi, Ankara, Turkey³ Stem Cell Institute, Ankara University, Balgat, Ankara, Turkey

* Authors to whom any correspondence should be addressed.

E-mail: dcansaran@ankara.edu.tr and ayilmazer@ankara.edu.tr**Keywords:** nanoparticle, ferroptosis, cell death, lipid peroxidation, ROS generation

Abstract

The use of nanomaterials for cancer ferroptosis presents a promising avenue for research and clinical applications. The unique properties of nanomaterials, such as their small size, large surface area, and ability to be engineered for specific tasks, make them ideal candidates for ferroptosis inducing cancer therapies. Ferroptosis is a new type of cell death mechanism that is distinct from apoptosis and necrosis. It has been shown to be critical in the treatment of various tumors. The ferroptotic mechanism has been mainly linked with the regulation of iron, amino acid, glutathione, and lipid metabolism of cells. The relationship between ferroptosis mechanisms and cancer nanomedicine has attracted considerable interest in recent years. It has been reported that the combination of nanomedicine and ferroptosis can achieve high therapeutic efficacy for the treatment of different cancer types. This review will provide an overview of recent work in ferroptosis-related cancer nanomedicine. First, general information is given about the definition of ferroptosis and its differences from other cell death mechanisms. Later, studies exploring the role of ferroptosis in the cancer nanomedicine field are discussed in detail. Specific focus has been given to the use of combinatorial treatment strategies which combine ferroptosis with chemodynamic therapy, photodynamic therapy, photothermal therapy, immunotherapy and sonodynamic therapy. Considering the fact that ferroptosis inducing nanoparticles (NPs) have already been introduced into clinical studies, nanoscientists can further accelerate this clinical translation as they tailor the physicochemical characteristics of nanomaterials. This review provides enlightening information for all researchers interested in the molecular characterization and relationship between ferroptosis and cancer-directed NPs.

Abbreviations List

4-HNE	4-hydroxynonenal
ACSF2	Acyl-CoA synthetase family member 2
Ag	Silver
ATP5G3	ATP synthase membrane subunit C locus 3
ATR3/4	Activating transcription factors 3/4
C57BL/6 mice	C57 black 6 mice
CD45	Protein tyrosine phosphatase
CDT	Chemodynamic therapy
CM	Cell membrane
CPT	Camptothecin
CS	Citrate synthase
CTLA-4	Cytotoxic T-lymphocyte associated protein 4

DFOM	Deferoxamine
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
FDA	Food and drug administration
Fe	Iron Ion
Fe ₃ O ₄	Iron(II,III) oxide/ferrous-ferric oxide
FePt	Iron–platinum
GPX4	Glutathione peroxidase 4
GR	Glutathione-disulfide reductase
GSDMD	Gasdermin D
GSH	Glutathione
GSSG	Oxidized glutathione
H ₂ O ₂	Hydrogen peroxide
IL-1b	Interleukin 1beta
IO	Iron oxide
IREB2	Iron responsive element binding protein 2
Keap1	Kelch-like ECH-associated protein 1
LDH	Lactate dehydrogenase
LIP	Labile iron pool
MAPK	Mitogen-activated protein kinase
MDA	Malondialdehyde
Mn-MOF	manganese porphyrin-based metal-organic framework
MnO ₂	Manganese dioxide
MnO _x	Manganese oxides
MOF	Metal-organic framework
mRNA	Messenger RNA
NADP+	Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate
NADPH	Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate hydrogen
ncRNA	Non-coding RNA
NFE2L2/NRF2	Nuclear factor erythroid 2-like factor 2
NIR	Near-infrared
nm	nanometer
NPs	Nanoparticles
NSG mice	NOD scid gamma <i>mice</i>
O ₂	Oxygen
OH	Hydroxyl radical
p62	Aquestosome 1
PD-1	Programmed cell death protein 1
PDL-1	Programmed death-ligand 1
PDT	Photodynamic therapy
PEG	Polyethylene glycol
pH	Potential/Power of hydrogen
PL	Piperlongumine
PL-PUFA	Phospholipid-polyunsaturated fatty acids
PL-PUFA-	Polyunsaturated-fatty-acid-containing-phospholipid hydroperoxides
OOH	
PTT	Photothermal therapy
PUFA	Polyunsaturated fatty acid
RAS	Rat sarcoma virus
RNA	Ribonucleic acid
ROS	Reactive oxygen species
RPL8	Ribosomal protein L8
RSL3/5	RAS-selective lethal 3/5
SDT	Sonodynamic therapy
SLC3A2	Solute carrier family 3 member 2
SLC7A11	Solute carrier family 7 member 11
SPC	Semiconductor polycomplex
SPFeN	Semiconductor polycomplex nanoparticles
TF	Transferrin
TFR	Transferrin receptor
TP53	Tumor protein 53
TPZ	Tirapazamine
TTC35	Tetratricopeptide repeat protein 35
US	Ultrasound

1. Introduction

Cell death is a physiological process that causes loss of cell integrity and inhibits metabolic functions, growth, and proliferation [1, 2]. Cell death mechanisms that play an important role in maintaining homeostasis are generally divided into programmed and unprogrammed cell death. Programmed cell death mechanisms such as apoptosis, autophagy and pyroptosis occur under the control of several biochemical mechanisms and many molecular factors [2, 3]. Conversely, unprogrammed cell death mechanisms such as necrosis are uncontrol processes that result in the dispersal of cell contents into surrounding tissues and cause inflammation [3]. Ferroptosis, a relatively newly discovered type of cell death, which is significantly different from apoptosis, autophagy, and necrosis [4, 5]. It is known that ferroptotic cell death has essential roles in the development or treatment of many diseases including nervous system diseases, kidney failure and cancer [5].

Inducers of ferroptosis, such as erastin, were determined before the identification of the ferroptosis pathway, one of the cell death pathways. The erastin molecule was discovered as a new chemical compound that causes the death of RAS-mutated tumor cells through a non-apoptotic process, and then the compounds RSL3 and RSL5, which have a similar effect, were revealed [6, 7]. In 2008, Yang and Stockwell suggested that cell death is inhibited by an iron chelator (DFOM) and an antioxidant (vitamin E) and that this is associated with the level of intracellular iron and reactive oxygen species (ROS) [6, 8]. In 2012, the concept of 'ferroptosis' was first used by Dixon *et al* to express cell death caused by the accumulation of iron-dependent lipid peroxides [4]. Then, the research efforts continued on elucidating the molecular mechanisms of ferroptosis and developing new ferroptosis-based treatment methods (figure 1).

The use of nanoparticles (NPs) in cancer therapy offers several advantages, including enhanced drug delivery, improved targeting, and reduced systemic toxicity [9–13]. NPs can be designed to specifically target cancer cells, thereby increasing the therapeutic efficacy and minimizing off-target effects [11, 12, 14, 15]. Furthermore, NPs can be engineered to trigger ferroptosis, providing a novel strategy for cancer treatment [10]. We will highlight the significance of the ferroptosis in the therapeutic potential of nanomaterials in this review article. We will review recent advances in ferroptosis inducer development, including small compounds and nanomaterials, as well as their design, mechanisms of action, and cancer therapeutic applications. We intend to present a thorough overview of the potential of nanomaterials in ferroptosis-based cancer therapy by reviewing the current literature.

2. Characteristic features of ferroptosis

Unlike other types of cell death mechanisms, ferroptosis is a new form of programmed cell death characterized by the iron-dependent accumulation of lipid peroxides in the cell [4, 16]. It has been reported that ferroptosis is morphologically, biochemically, immunologically, and genetically distinct from other cell death mechanisms. Reduction of cell volume and mitochondria, decrease or disappearance of mitochondrial crystals, increase in mitochondrial membrane potential can be given as features of morphological differences in ferroptosis [4, 17, 18]. When examined biochemically, changes such as increased intracellular ROS, lipid peroxides, and unstable iron ion levels are observed in ferroptotic cell death compared to other cell death types [19]. In addition, the fact that genes such as *TTC35*, *CS*, *ACSF2*, *ATP5G3*, *IREB2* and *RPL8* have regulatory roles in the ferroptosis process shows that the ferroptosis mechanism is controlled by a different genetic mechanism than other cell death pathways [19, 20]. Furthermore, ferroptosis causes immune and inflammatory reactions different from other types of cell death in the state of damage such as tissue injury [19]. Morphological, biochemical, genetic, and immune differences of ferroptosis distinguish it from other types of cell death.

3. Molecular mechanisms of ferroptosis

Ferroptosis is closely associated with iron metabolism, lipid metabolism, and glutathione metabolism, which governs cystine uptake into the cell [5, 16, 19]. Iron ions have important roles in the regulation of energy metabolism in the cell, enzymatic processes, and other metabolic functions within the cell [21, 22]. Under normal conditions, iron metabolism is tightly controlled by factors such as transcription factors, cytokines, and hormones [5, 22]. Excessive levels of iron in the cell can cause serious damage to the cell and tissues. Disturbances in iron metabolism have been associated with neurodegenerative disorders and cardiovascular diseases [22]. In the process of ferroptosis, a high amount of free iron ion (Fe^{+2}) accumulation is observed in the cell. Increased Fe^{+2} level in the cell, is provided by the increase of iron uptake from the extracellular space to the cytoplasm via transferrin (TF) and the TF receptor and/or the release of Fe^{+2} by the breakdown of ferritins where excess iron stored in the cell though lysosomes [5, 23]. Excessive increase in the level of Fe^{+2} ions in the cell leads to the production of superoxide radicals and ROS by the Fenton reaction [23]. This

causes lipid peroxidation reactions that damage the cell membrane and causes ferroptosis sensitivity in the cell [18, 23–25].

Lipid peroxidation, another mechanism that plays an important role in the induction of ferroptosis, is a reaction that causes oxidative damage to cell membranes, organelle membranes, and other lipid-containing molecules [5, 18, 23]. Increased intracellular lipid peroxidation is closely associated with many diseases such as neurodegenerative disorders, ischemia-reperfusion injury, and cancer [26]. Fatty acids are structural components of biological membranes and are involved in cellular processes such as signal transduction and energy metabolism. Polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) are necessary substrates for lipid oxidation to occur [4, 18]. Therefore, the increase in the amount of free PUFAs in the cell leads to lipid peroxidation, which is one of the important causes of ferroptosis [18]. The abundance of oxidative stress, lipid peroxidation and lipid peroxidation products such as malondialdehyde (MDA) and 4-hydroxynonenal in the cell leads to the induction of ferroptotic cell death mechanism, unlike other types of cell death [5, 18, 23].

The ‘system Xc-/GSH/GPX4 axis’ called glutathione metabolism, is an important antioxidant system in cells [24]. The system consists of Xc-, SLC3A2, and SLC7A11 and is located in the cell membrane as an antiporter that takes cystine into the cell, which is necessary for glutathione (GSH) synthesis [25–27]. GSH, which is composed of glycine, glutamate and cystine, is an important antioxidant molecule that prevents the accumulation of lipid ROS in the cell [24, 27]. Glutathione peroxidase (GPX4) is a GSH-dependent antioxidant system element that converts lipid hydroperoxides to lipid alcohols. Inhibition of system Xc- or decreased expression of SLC7A11 in the cell prevents cystine uptake into the cell [5, 23, 24]. This causes a decrease in the GSH level and increases the accumulation of ROS and lipid ROS in the cell. Increasing reactive oxygen levels decreases GPX4 activity, reducing the capacity of the intracellular antioxidant system, which leads to the induction of ferroptosis [5, 25]. System Xc-inhibitors such as erastin, glutamate, and sorafenib have been identified as molecules that increase ferroptosis sensitivity in the cell in this way [27, 28].

Apart from the GSH mechanism, which also includes iron and lipid metabolism, antioxidant and oxidant system elements, the sulfur transfer pathway, heat shock proteins and mitogen-activated protein kinase

signaling pathway are also involved in the regulation of the ferroptosis mechanism [5, 29]. The ferroptosis process is also controlled and regulated by various transcription factors. Examples of these transcription factors are tumor protein 53 (TP53), nuclear factor erythroid 2-like factor 2 (NFE2L2), and activating transcription factors 3 and 4 (ATF3, ATF4) [30, 31]. Epigenetic regulation mechanisms also play a role in determining ferroptosis sensitivity within the cell [31]. DNA methylations, such as chromatin remodeling, and histone modifications, such as histone ubiquitination, affect the tendency of cells to undergo ferroptosis [32, 33]. Non-coding RNAs that can also directly or indirectly affect DNA, mRNA and proteins by being involved in basic regulatory mechanisms are also involved in the regulation of the ferroptosis pathway [34, 35]. Understanding the regulatory pathways of ferroptosis will enable the development of new treatment strategies for many diseases, mainly cancer.

4. Ferroptosis inducers in cancer treatment: chemotherapy, radiotherapy and immunotherapy

Chemotherapy is a long-used traditional method of treating cancer in which various drugs are used to destroy cancer cells that divide uncontrollably. Chemotherapy agents are primarily targeted at disrupting the cell cycle or DNA replication [36, 37]. Researchers focused on revealing alternative treatment approaches to increase the effectiveness of chemotherapy treatment. In recent years, studies on ferroptosis-targeted approach have begun as one of the alternative pathways [38, 39]. Conventional chemotherapy agents trigger cellular stress to destroy cancer cells. Many chemotherapeutic drugs, such as platinum compounds and anthracyclines, produce ROS. This oxidative stress can disrupt cellular redox homeostasis and potentially trigger pathways such as ferroptosis [40–42].

The use of some chemotherapeutics in tumor cells can lead to drug resistance over time. Chemotherapeutic drug resistance may block the ferroptosis mechanism, and the effect of the cell death process can be reduced. Additionally, it has been revealed that many FDA-approved cancer drugs act on tumor cells by inducing ferroptosis [43]. Erastin, a ferroptosis inducer, increases the effectiveness of some chemotherapeutics such as temozolomide, cisplatin, vemurafenib and docetaxel in suppressing cancer cells [44–47]. Cisplatin, a chemotherapeutic drug used in the treatment of various cancers, induces ferroptosis, as do the ferroptosis activators erastin and RSL3. The mechanism of action of cisplatin is through GPX inactivation and GSH depletion, thus increasing the accumulation of ROS and lipid peroxidation in cells and activating ferroptosis [48, 49]. Sorafenib, a targeted anti-cancer drug, is the first clinically approved chemotherapy drug proven to induce ferroptosis [50–52]. Sorafenib activates ferroptosis in two different ways: the first is by suppressing cystine uptake, reducing the GSH level and increasing lipid ROS accumulation, and the second is by affecting the p62-Keap1-NRF2 pathway and regulating redox and iron metabolism [53, 54]. FDA-approved sulfasalazine and lanperisone, with a similar mechanism of action, induce ferroptosis by inhibiting the cystine uptake activity of system Xc- and promoting GSH depletion, thus suppressing cancer cell proliferation [55, 56]. The combination of lapatinib, a chemotherapy drug used in the treatment of breast cancer, and siramesine induces ferroptosis through iron metabolism by decreasing ferroportin and ferritin expression and increasing intracellular iron ion accumulation by increasing TF expression [57, 58]. With traditional chemotherapy and ferroptosis modulation approach, better therapeutic results on cancer can be achieved and it may be possible to develop more effective and targeted cancer treatments.

Radiotherapy is one of the cancer treatment methods that uses ionizing radiation such as x-ray and γ -rays to destroy malignant cells or control uncontrolled cell proliferation. After the application of ionizing radiation, the rays cause the emergence of free radicals through the radiolysis of water to control cell proliferation [59]. Many studies have determined that sorafenib and sulfasalazine, which are among the FDA-approved chemotherapeutics, stimulate the ferroptosis mechanism with radiation application in different types of cancer such as lung cancer, melanoma and breast cancer [60–62]. It has been revealed in studies in the literature that RSL3 and erastin, which are ferroptosis inducers, increase the radiation efficiency in different cancer types [43, 62].

Immunotherapy is a cancer treatment method that has been used frequently in recent years. Programmed cell death protein 1 (PD-1) and programmed cell death ligand 1 (PD-L1) inhibitors are most commonly used in immunotherapy treatment to prevent PD-1 on the surface of T cells. With the application of immunotherapy, cancer cells escape from T cells and restore the T cell killing function towards cancer cells. Thus, the disease is suppressed by the destruction of cancer cells. In one of the first ferroptosis inducing immunotherapy studies, the objective of the research was to provide PD-L1 to NSG and C57BL/6 mice that had ovarian tumors originating from ID8 cells [63]. PD-L1 blockade therapy in *in vivo* tests resulted in an elevation of ROS only in CD45- ID8 cells, while no such rise was detected in CD45+ cells. A statistically significant rise in ROS was observed, with a *p*-value of 0.0014. The progression of the tumor was tracked by

measuring the total flux, which represents the number of photons emitted every second. The p -value on day 40 is less than 0.0001. *In vivo*, the impact of the ferroptosis inhibitor liproxstatin-1 on the effectiveness of checkpoint blockade was also examined. The researchers showed that the use of both anti-CTLA-4 and anti-PD-L1 checkpoint blockers successfully decreased the growth of B16 tumors in mice treated with DMSO, liproxstatin-1, a combination therapy of anti-CTLA-4 and anti-PD-L1, or a combination therapy of anti-CTLA-4, anti-PD-L1, and liproxstatin-1. This reduction in tumor growth was statistically significant, with a p -value of 0.0008 for the former group and a p -value of less than 0.0001 for the latter group. Therefore, it was shown that the efficacy of immunotherapy was enhanced via the ferroptosis mechanism. The growing body of research on ferroptosis has the potential to facilitate the development of novel and efficacious therapeutic approaches to combat cancer.

5. The relationship of nanomaterials with ferroptosis pathway in cancer treatment

In contrast to conventional cancer therapy procedures, innovative therapeutic strategies using nanomaterials have been developed for many years. Despite significant technological progress in this field, there are some obstacles to nanomedicine to be translated to clinical settings. These include complexity of tumor biology, partial elucidation of nano-bio interfaces, and challenges in material chemistry, manufacturing, and clinical and commercialization [64]. Therefore, to increase the efficacy of these cancer-directed NPs, researchers are trying to explore different combinational strategies including immunotherapies, photodynamic or photothermal therapies [65]. Therefore, harboring different mechanisms to augment the anti-tumor potential of NPs have been studied in various reports [66]. Ferroptosis is a promising new cancer therapy target, and NPs offer many advantages for the delivery of ferroptosis inducers to tumors [67]. Technological innovations and biomedical developments for cancer treatment have a great potential for innovative cancer treatment types. Various studies show the potential of NPs to trigger ferroptosis in cancer cells. There is a growing body of research indicating the significant potential of using ferroptosis induction as a basis for cancer treatment. Ferroptosis is a novel kind of non-apoptotic cell death characterized by the buildup of ROS and lipid peroxidation, both of which are reliant on iron [68–70]. Recently, several studies have been conducted focusing on the discovery, mechanisms, and applications of ferroptosis in cancer treatment, due to its effective antitumor activity when integrated with biotechnology in the field of nanotechnology [71–73]. Table 1 summarizes the studies focusing on the ferroptosis inducing nanomaterials, by giving details of the *in vitro*, *in vivo* tumor models used, proposed mechanisms and major results obtained [74–153].

Nanomaterials can induce ferroptosis by arming various different mechanisms (figure 2). Zhang *et al* conducted an initial investigation on the relationship between ferroptosis and NPs. They demonstrated a targeted and efficient cancer treatment approach by using a Fenton reaction triggered by certain characteristics of the tumor microenvironment. The study involves the ionization of amorphous iron NPs for on-demand ferrous ion release and subsequent H_2O_2 disproportionation for efficient $\cdot OH$ generation [154]. This study was one of the first to demonstrate that NPs could induce ferroptosis, and it opened up a new area of research into the potential use of NPs for cancer therapy. Various other studies showed that IO NPs can be used to induce ferroptosis in a variety of cancer cells. For example, Li *et al* used ferroptosis as a means to inhibit the proliferation of a tumor. A nanocarrier containing artemisinin, a compound that triggers ferroptosis, was synthesized in this research. The nanocarrier exhibited pH-dependent activation in the drug release tests using TA-Fe/ART@ZIF, and demonstrated excellent release performance. The presence of elevated levels of intracellular ROS and MDA, together with reduced levels of GSH and GPX4, indicates the activation of a newly discovered nano-drug system that enhances the process of ferroptosis (figure 3). The *in vitro* cytotoxicity testing revealed that the viability of the MDA-MB-231 cell line was decreased by roughly 60% when treated with the produced carrier. To conduct a more detailed analysis of the therapeutic impact in live studies, tumors and other healthy tissues were subjected to a 14 d treatment. It was observed that the experimental groups did not experience any significant alteration in body weight. However, the tumor size in the experimental group treated with TA-Fe/ART@ZIF NPs was approximately one third smaller compared to the other groups. Therefore, the results of *in vitro* investigations on different cell types were validated by conducting tests on *in vivo* tumor modification [74]. In addition to Fe-based Fenton nanocatalysts, other nano systems have also recently been reported to induce Fenton-like chemical reactions, including Ag NPs, MnOx-based NPs [155]. For example, Lin *et al* synthesized MnO₂-coated mesoporous silica NPs (designated as MS@MnO₂), in which the MnO₂ component reacted with increased GSH in cancer cells inducing Fenton-like activity to directly transform intracellular H_2O_2 into highly toxic $\cdot OH$ [156]. GSH consumption in this study inhibited its ability to scavenge hydroxyl radicals. *In vitro* chemodynamic toxicity tests showed that mesoporous silica NPs with hydrophobic anticancer drug camptothecin reduced the viability of cancer cells by 80%. It also improved Fenton-based therapeutic efficacy, which was demonstrated by effective anti-tumor activity *in vivo* (table 1).

Table 1. Nanomaterial based ferroptosis studies.

Nanomaterial	<i>In vitro</i> model	<i>In vivo</i> model	Mechanisms & outcomes	Ref.
GA-Fe(II)+DOX	MCF-7/ADR	MCF-7/ADR	GSH deficiency caused the onset of iron-induced ferroptosis and chemotherapeutic resistance was reduced via the Fenton reaction.	[153]
FeCO-DOX@MCN	MCF-7, A549, HeLa	MCF-7	Ferroptosis occurred due to the increased ROS levels and iron overload, as well as GSH depletion and GPX4 inactivation.	[76]
Fe (III)-ART NPs	A549	A549	The nanoparticle was triggered by intracellular GSH, leading to the reduction of iron elements. The resulting GSH depletion reduced the antioxidation of tumors and increased CDT.	[141]
SPFeN	4T1	4T1	The Fenton reaction together with PTT took place as a consequence of the reduction of the iron element.	[108]
FePt@MoS ₂	4T1, L02, MCF-7, HeLa, BRL-3A	4T1	The Fenton reaction caused the trigger of PTT and tumor immunotherapy.	[77]
PEG-Fns	SCC-7	4T1	Nanoformulation was activated by blue light which resulted in iron release to produce ROS. Along with apoptosis and ferroptosis, the treatment protocol inhibited the tumor's development and stopped pulmonary metastasis.	[78]
SRF@Fe ^{III} TA	4T1, CT26, SCC-7, HepG2, HT1080, (3T3, COS7, NCTC1469)	4T1	After inactivation of GPX4 enzyme, iron ions produced by ferroptosis are reduced and lipid peroxides are produced by redox reaction.	[79]
FePt/BP-PEI-FA	4T1, MCF-7, L02	4T1	PTT was combined with PDT and immunotherapy protocols. ROS production was detected as a result of Fenton reaction.	[80]
DOX/EGCG-Fe	LL2, A549, L929	LL2	The nanoformulation caused the reduction of ferrous ions to induce the continuous production of ROS through the Fenton reaction using chemotherapy and thus trigger ferroptosis.	[81]
Fe(III)-GA/GOx@ZIF-Azo	MCF-7	MCF-7	The protocol initiated by PTT led to the reduction of iron by the Fenton reaction and ongoing ROS production resulted in ferroptosis.	[82]
Fe-PDA@LAP-PEG-cRGD	B16F10	B16F10	NIR-mediated PTT effect caused ferroptotic damage through increasing lipid peroxidation.	[83]
PtH@FeP	4T1, HepG2, A2780	4T1	Combinatorial treatment with Fenton reaction, PTT and chemotherapy resulted in increased ferroptosis by increasing the level of lipid peroxidate through GPX4 suppression.	[84]
bcc-USINPs	HepG2- MC38	HepG2, MC38	Iron accumulation induced ferroptosis via the Fenton reaction and enhanced immunotherapy.	[85]
PCGA@FeNP	4T1	4T1	The realization of the Fenton reaction with the decrease of GPX4 triggered ferroptosis and PTT.	[87]
FePPy NP	HeLa	HeLa	Following the PTT protocol, iron accumulation, and lipid peroxidation resulted in ferroptosis.	[88]
BCFe@SRF	Hepa 1-6, NIH 3T3	Hepa 1-6	Following PDT, SRF is released in response to the disruption of the tumor antioxidant defense system, while ferritin was released by the iron-catalyzed Fenton reaction.	[89]
CaFe@DMSN/C NPs	4T1, RAW264.7	4T1	The nanoformulation employed caused the Fenton reaction and enhanced the OH radicals to cause ferroptosis based immunotherapy.	[90]
DOX-Fe(VI)@HMS-HE-PEG	Saos-2	Saos-2	Chemotherapy drug release increased under US irradiation. US responsive Oxygen/ROS generation and GSH depletion triggered ferroptosis.	[91]
FePt@COP-FA(FPMCF NPs)	MCF-7, 4T1, L02	4T1	The formation of hydroxyl radicals following the PTT protocol activated the ferroptosis pathway resulting in lipid peroxide accumulation and ferroptotic cell death. This also triggered immunotherapy.	[130]

(Continued.)

Table 1. (Continued.)

	Nanomaterial	<i>In vitro</i> model	<i>In vivo</i> model	Mechanisms & outcomes	Ref.
Combinational nanoplatforams	FePtMn-Ce6/FA	4T1, MCF-7	4T1	Responding to tumor microenvironment, NPs released Iron ions to catalyze H ₂ O ₂ to OH by Fenton reaction and catalyzed hydrogen peroxide (H ₂ O ₂) to O ₂ , providing PDT, and PTT under different wavelength lights.	[92]
	FePt-PTTA-Eu3+-FA (FPEF)	4T1, MCF-7, HepG2, A549, HeLa, BRL3A, L02	4T1	Induction of the Fenton reaction by ROS formation caused ferroptosis.	[93]
	FePt@MnO@DSPE-PEG 5000-FA	4T1, HeLa, L02	4T1	CDT triggered ferroptosis based anticancer therapy based on the Fenton reaction with ROS formation.	[94]
	RSL3@COF-Fc(2b)	HT-1080, MCF-7, HCT-116, MCF-10A	HT-1080	Following iron accumulation by CDT, GPX activity decreased and GSH levels decreased which resulted in ferroptosis.	[95]
	CaP-DOX@Fe2+-siMCT4-PEG-HA	4T1, MCF-7	MCF7,	In addition to chemotherapy, ferroptosis occurred with high lipid ROS levels and H ₂ O ₂ catalysis.	[96]
	NMIL-100@GOx@C	4T1	4T1	GSH reduced Iron ion, generating OH radicals by the Fenton reaction, resulting in ferroptosis and starvation therapy.	[98]
	PFP@Fe/Cu-SS	Huh-7	Huh-7	As a result of the Fenton reaction following PTT, GPX4 activity was inhibited and GSH depletion occurred.	[99]
	Fe-CO@Mito-PNBE	HeLa, 4T1	Not applicable	The production of ROS with the release of denir ions triggers the Fenton reaction.	[100]
	Fn-DOX	HepG2, HT29	Not applicable	The nanopharmaceutical used for ferroptosis induction induced ROS accumulation and cell ferroptosis.	[101]
	Holo-Lf	MDA-MB-231, MCF-7	MDA-MB-231	Iron release increased ROS production and consequently enhanced ferroptosis.	[102]
NFER	PC12, 4T1, L929	4T1	Chemotherapy and its ability to induce lipid peroxidation resulted in ferroptosis.	[103]	
ZVI@Ag and ZVI@CMC	H1299, H460, A549, LLC, MRC-5, IMR-90	A549, H460, LLC	The viability of cancer cells was reduced via ferroptosis as a result of ZVI-NP-induced mitochondrial dysfunction, intracellular oxidative stress and lipid peroxidation.	[104]	
Single nanoplatforams	TA-Fe/ART@ZIF	MDA-MB-231 and L929	MDA-MB-23	Increased intracellular ROS, along with a decline in GSH and GPX4, led to ferroptosis in cancer cells.	[74]
	Fe-NQA NPs	CT26, 4T1, HeLa, HUVEC, AML-12, L02	CT26	Ferroptosis occurred as a result of the Fenton reaction and GPX4 inhibition.	[105]
	UPDA-PEG@Fe ^{2+/3+}	4T1, U87MG	4T1	ROS and lipid peroxidation formation triggered ferroptosis.	[106]
	LPOgener	MCF-7, 4T1, L02	4T1	Formation of lipid peroxidation under high GSH level resulted in ferroptosis in cancer cells.	[107]
	ZVI@CMC	OEC-M1, OC3, SCC9, HSC-3, SAS, KOSC-3, OC2, hNOK	SAS	ROS overload resulted in the oxidative conversion of iron ions, which is followed by ferroptosis induced by mitochondrial lipid peroxidation.	[109]
	WA-NP	CHP-134, CHP-212, IMR-32, Kelly, NB69, NLE, SH-EP, SH-SY5Y, SK-N-AS, SK-N-BE(2)C, SK-N-DZ, SK-N-SH	IMR-32	Increasing unstable Iron ion through targeting GPX4 and/or excessive HMOX1 activation resulted in ferroptosis.	[110]

(Continued.)

Combinational nanoplatforms	Iron oxide nanoformulations	GBP@Fe ₃ O ₄	C4-2	C4-2	In the laser-heated cells, the Fenton reaction occurred, which prevented GSH formation. Tumor ferroptosis was triggered.	[86]
		CoFe ₂ O ₄	HUVECs, L929, 4T1	4T1	Lipid peroxidation was observed as a result of SDT and CDT and the Fenton reaction triggered ferroptosis.	[111]
		Fe ₃ O ₄ -SAS@PLT	4T1	4T1	Immunotherapy induced a ferroptotic cell death by blocking the glutamate-cystine antiporter system Xc- pathway.	[119]
		Pt-FMO	HeLa	HeLa	In addition to iron ion release, additional rise in cellular H ₂ O ₂ levels significantly strengthened ferroptosis through intracellular Fenton reactions.	[112]
		FeOOH NSs	4T1, CT26	4T1, CT26	Ferroptosis-mediated depletion of GPX4 resulted in the immediate killing of tumor cells following PTT.	[113]
		Fe ₃ O ₄ -PLGA-Ce6	4T1	4T1	In addition to increased ROS concentration and GSH depletion after PDT, GPX4 levels decreased and lipid peroxidation levels increased, which resulted in Ferroptosis.	[114]
		HCSV	TRAMP-C1	TRAMP-C1	Fenton reaction-mediated ferroptosis induced immunogenic response through increasing iron ions via redox reaction.	[115]
		Pt&Fe ₃ O ₄ @PP	U87MG	U87MG	Fenton reaction generated potent ROS to initiate ferroptosis and chemotherapy.	[116]
		SRF@MPDA-SPIO	HCT-116, HUVEC	HCT-116	ROS are produced as part of the ferroptosis mechanism by the iron-based Fenton reaction and PTT.	[117]
		FA/Pt-si-GPX4@IONPs	U87MG, P3 GBM, NHA	U87MG	Gene therapy and chemotherapy inhibited GPX4 expression of co-released si-GPX4 GPX4, while the Fenton reaction generated potent ROS to initiate ferroptosis.	[118]
		CSO-BHQ-IR780-Hex/MIONPs/Sor	4T1, MCF-7	4T1, MCF-7	NIR irradiation increased the iron supply in the cells, triggered the xCT/GSH/GPX-4 system, and induced a large number of lipid peroxidation bursts, leading to ferroptosis in the cell.	[120]
		Fe ₃ O ₄ -C@MnOx@PEI@iRGD+DOX	MDA-MB-231, HDF, ADSC, C2C12, HeLa, DU-145	MDA-MB-231	Following PTT and CDT, the gradual depletion of GSH and termination of self-activated ROS production via the Fenton reaction resulted in ferroptosis.	[121]
Iron free nanoformulations		NSs@DCPy	MC38	MC38	Iron overload, GSH depletion resulted in cancer cell ferroptosis by PDT.	[122]
		PFTT@CM	MDA-MB-231, RAW 264.7, HCT116, PATU8988, HeLa	MDA-MB-231	Iron ion decreased GSH levels and generated •OH, which increased the PDT effect and caused cell death.	[97]
		GCMNPs	Kasumi-1, U937, MV4-11, NB4, HT29, Caco-2, SW480	C1498, CT26	Ferroptosis was brought on by GCMNPs, and levels of lipid peroxides went up. Additionally, the treatment protocol enhanced T-cell immunological response.	[123]
		Tf-LipoMof@PL	4T1	4T1	Ferroptosis and pyroptosis were both treated simultaneously. Due to ferroptosis, GPX4 was reduced, lipid peroxidation was induced, and Fenton reactions were stimulated due to elevated ROS levels.	[75]
		CSO-SS-Cy7-Hex/SPION/Srfrn	4T1	4T1	Using the oxidation/reduction response, GSH was reduced, ROS generation was enhanced, and Fenton reaction was formed.	[124]
		SRF@Hb-Ce6	4T1, HepG2, A549, MCF-10A,	4T1	Decreased GPX4 and increased lipid peroxidation resulted in a combination of oxygen-assisted PDT and Iron-assisted ferroptosis.	[125]
		Mn-MOF	H22, 4T1	H22, 4T1	After US irradiation, it lost GSH and GPX4 and encouraged iron overload and ROS production in hypoxic tumors.	[152]
		Pd SAzyme	4T1	4T1	Ferroptosis is caused by increased ROS production, OH production and GSH consumption.	[126]

(Continued.)

Table 1. (Continued.)

	Nanomaterial	<i>In vitro</i> model	<i>In vivo</i> model	Mechanisms & outcomes	Ref.	
Combinational nanoplatfoms	Iron free nanoformulations	DS@MA-LS	4T1, HUVEC, RAW264.7	4T1	Increased ROS formation led to inhibition of GSH synthesis, resulting in ferroptosis.	[127]
		NLC/H(D + F + S) NPs +DOX	4T1, 3T3	4T1, 3T3	Apoptosis was caused by an increase in ROS during ferroptosis, which enhanced the effect of chemotherapy and stimulated the anti-tumor immune response.	[128]
		mPEG-PLys-AA/RSL3	NCI-ADR/Res (NAR)	NCI-ADR, Res (NAR)	Ferroptotic cell death in the presence of chemotherapy was triggered by GSH depletion in the presence of ROS.	[129]
		Ce6@CMOF	4T1	4T1	Ferroptosis was initiated and depleted by GSH of the highly reactive single oxygen in PDT.	[131]
		Supramolecular Ce6-erastin nanodrug	CAL-27	CAL-27	The triggering of ROS production by PDT induced iron accumulation and GPX4, resulting in Ferroptosis.	[132]
		BNP@R,	B16-F10, CT26, 4T1, T cell	4T1, B16-F10	Tumor cells were primed for GPX4-associated ferroptosis by PDT and iron accumulation was observed, leading to an immunogenic response.	[133]
		TMB-F4TCNQ and TMB-TCNQ	4T1, HeLa	4T1	GSH biosynthesis was inhibited under NIR, ROS-mediated ferroptosis was induced.	[134]
		Pt-AuNS	TRAMP-C1, MCF-10A, MCF-7, MCF-7	MCF-7, ADR	PTT caused lipid peroxidation and GSH depletion and GPX4 inactivation caused ferroptosis.	[135]
		HMCMS	MCF-7, MDA-MB-231, MGC-803	MCF-7	As a result of PTT, manganese ions are released, which promotes lipid peroxidation and ferroptosis.	[136]
		MnOx NS	4T1	4T1	Dual induction of CDT and GSH-depleting ferroptosis resulted in immunological response.	[137]
		Pa-M/Ti-NC	J774A.1, B16F10, 4T1	B16F10, 4T1	Fenton process using the freed Iron ions from magnetic nanocluster. The produced hydroxyl radicals then cause fatal ferroptosis an immunogenic response.	[138]
		HSN	4T1, MCF-7, HepG2, 3T3, NDF, MDA-MB-231, PC12, HeLa, SKOV3	4T1	The temperature increase caused by PTT resulted in the release of iron ions and an increase in OH radicals, causing ferroptosis in the cell.	[139]
Azo-CA4	MDA-MB-231	MDA-MB-231	As a result of chemotherapy, lipid peroxidation occurred due to the decrease in iron ions, resulting in ferroptosis.	[140]		
Single nanoplatfoms	DHM@RSL3	4T1	4T1	The cofactors GSH and Trx of GPX4, the primary enzyme in the ferroptotic lipid peroxide repair pathway, were depleted following a significant decrease in NADPH concentration, leading to ferroptosis.	[142]	
	GOx/BSO@CS PVs	EC, 4T1	4T1	With the depletion of GSH, the activity of GPX4 was inhibited and consequently the level of intracellular LPOs increased leading to ferroptosis.	[143]	
	LDL-DHA	PLC/PRF/5, HepG2, H4IIE	HepG2	Lipid peroxidation, glutathione depletion and glutathione peroxidase-4 inactivation promoted ferroptosis.	[144]	
	mSiO ₂ @MnO _x	PANC1, 4T1, L929	PANC1	Rising lipid peroxides levels, GSH depletion inactivated GPX4 and caused ferroptosis.	[145]	
	MMSNs@SO	HepG2, L02	Not applicable	GSH-depletion, inactivation of GPX-4, increase of lipid peroxides caused tumor cell death by ferroptosis.	[146]	
	FaPEG-MMSNs@DHA	HepG2, SKOV3, L02	HepG2, SKOV3	Ferroptosis was caused by the drop in GSH and the completion of the Fenton reaction.	[147]	
FeGd-HN@Pt@LF/RGD2	U-87, MCF-7	U-87, HBEC-5	The developed magnetic nanoparticles accelerated the Fenton reaction and caused the production of ROS for cell death.	[148]		

(Continued.)

Table 1. (Continued.)

Single nanoplatforms	FaPEG-MnMSN@SFB	L02, HUVEC, HepG2, A549, 4T1,	HepG2	The breakdown of MnMSN led to the depletion of GSH, the inhibition of GSH production by SFB, the induction of apoptosis and ferroptosis. [149]
	VZnO nanoparticles	HCT116, SW480, HT29, MC38, CT26, NCM460, SKOV3, 4T1, MCF-10A, H1299, B16F10	CT26, 4T1,	Cell death by ferroptosis was mediated by lipid peroxidation with decreased GSH level. [150]
	BPQDs	A549, BEAS-2B, H1299, HEK293T, HacaT	Not applicable	Ferroptosis was triggered by mitochondrial dysfunction, lipid peroxidation, and iron overload. [151]

6. Combination of ferroptosis with photodynamic and photothermal therapy (PTT)

With the widespread use of nanomaterials in cancer therapy, nanoscientists have developed combinational approaches to arm different cancer-killing strategies in one NP system. In the study of multifunctional NPs, the NPs (Fn-Dox) were loaded with the ferroptosis inducer ferritin and the apoptosis inducer doxorubicin. The NPs were able to induce both ferroptosis and apoptosis in HT29 human colorectal adenocarcinoma cells, leading to synergistic cell death. They have shown that the expression of GPX4 was significantly reduced in response to Fn-Dox (figure 4) [101]. In a different investigation, Xu *et al* combined non-apoptotic ferroptosis and pyroptosis death processes the nano drug formulation represented as Tf-LipoMof@PL, was developed to achieve ferroptosis/pyroptosis-mediated anticancer activity with a metal-organic framework (MOF) loaded with piperlongumine (PL) covered with a pH-sensitive lipid layer. By using the iron-containing MOF, it was intended to dramatically raise the iron content. PL used as a ferroptosis inducer, increased ferroptotic cell death in the study. It was also found that ROS production was increased through Fenton reactions. Ferroptosis and pyroptosis were successfully induced, according to the *in vitro* and *in vivo* results. Ferroptosis was validated by GPX4 depletion and elevation of lipid peroxidation, while pyroptosis

Figure 3. Artemisinin containing nanocarriers inducing ferroptosis. (A) The schematic representation of the study approach [74]. (B) ROS levels were imaged by DCFDA assay in MDA-MB-231 cells treated with ART, TA-Fe/ZIF, and TA-Fe/ART@ZIF nanoparticles. (C) Same treatment groups were also analyzed for the relative levels of MDA, GSH and GPX4 expression. Reproduced from [74], with permission from Springer Nature.

was confirmed by accelerated GSDMD cleavage and an increase in IL-1b and LDH. To evaluate the *in vivo* anti-tumor activity, tumor volumes of 4T1 xenograft mice were monitored for 21 d. In tumor volumes, the tumor volume of the control group reached 1500 mm³, while the tumor volume treated with Tf-LipoMof@PL did not reach 500 mm³ [75]. In this study, cancer cells were under localized light. It was concluded that the Fenton reaction in the tumor by exposing it to the 808 nm laser resulted in the production of ROS and ferroptosis as a result of the Fe₃O₄ explosion [86].

The basic principle in the treatment of cancer with photodynamic therapy (PDT) is the activation of the photosensitizer used under light applied at a certain wavelength, causing the formation of cytotoxic species, especially ROS, in the presence of oxygen, causing cell death [157, 158]. The main reason for the use of PDT as a cancer treatment is its basic specificity and selectivity [159]. An ideal photosensitizer is selective for tumor cells, it is physically and chemically stable. It also reaches tumor tissues in a short time, activates at a specific wavelength, and aims to be easily removed from the body [160]. ROS-mediated mechanism, which is a chemically reactive radical, forms the basis of the PDT method. Because the increase in the amount of ROS in the cell disrupts the structural lipid, protein and, DNA structure in the cell, impairing the vital functions of the cell [161]. Recent studies showed that PDT can kill cancer cells by a variety of mechanisms, including ferroptosis. For instance, Pan *et al* in their studies, it was loaded with hypoxia-activated prodrug tirapazamine to increase the efficiency of PDT and to trigger ferroptosis in cancer cells and formed a cancer cell membrane (CM). They called this nanocomposite they created PFTT@CM. By activating PFTT@CM by Tme, the nano platform triggered ferroptosis and significantly increased PDT activity using the Fenton reaction, which increased OH and O₂ formation as well as GSH depletion and ferroptosis. It was then exposed to various light wavelengths to enhance the effects of PDT [97].

PTT is another method popularly used for cancer treatment [162]. Nanomaterials used in PTT can efficiently absorb near-infrared (NIR) light and convert it into heat, leading to the targeted destruction of cancer cells while minimizing damage to healthy tissues [163]. The photo agents used expose cancer cells to temperatures higher than 42 °C, resulting in necrosis and apoptosis [164, 165]. Localized heat generation generated by PTT can support different treatments. For example, it increases the permeability of membranes, augmenting the accumulation of combinatorial treatments such as chemotherapy [166–168]. In one study, He *et al* created iron-chelated semiconductor polycomplex NPs (SPFeN) and employed them as a ferroptosis initiator for photothermal ferrotherapy of cancer. The hybrid polymeric nano agent used in the

study contains (Fe^{+3}) as a ferroptosis inducer and also contains an amphiphilic semiconductor polycomplex with the function of both a PTT nano transducer and an iron ion chelator. The accumulation of NPs *in vivo* mouse tumor tissue was seen to be caused by poly (ethylene glycol) grafting and their small size. When utilized for PTT, the NIR speeds up the Fenton reactions and produces a localized heat source for PTT (figure 5). The produced NPs produce hydroxyl radicals that lead to ferroptosis [108].

7. Combination of ferroptosis with immunotherapy

Cancer immunotherapy is a treatment strategy that employs the body's immune system to recognize and eliminate tumor cells. Unlike other treatment methods, the primary goal of immunotherapy is to prevent the metastatic spread of the disease and to improve the quality of life of individuals. On the other hand, the working principle of immunotherapy is stimulating the immune system and supporting it with different compounds [169]. The main purpose of cancer immunotherapy is to educate both the immune cells in the tumor microenvironment and in lymphoid tissues to destroy cancer cells. Another advantage of immunotherapy is that it can create long-term immune memory and may help prevent disease recurrence. Studies have shown that nano-sized materials can support active tumor targeting [170, 171]. Studies have been conducted to create combined treatment strategies that combine immunotherapy with ferroptosis in addition to those for the treatment of cancer with immunotherapy. Ferroimmunotherapy is also regarded to have the potential to boost the immune response. For instance, Jiang *et al* studied how to induce ferroptosis and immunogenicity. In this study, 4T1 breast cancer was treated by using Fe_3O_4 -SAS @ PLT NPs in both *in vivo* and *in vitro* conditions (figure 6). With Fe_3O_4 -SAS@PLT, iron accumulation has been claimed to

enhance the Fenton reaction and effectively repolarize macrophages from the immunosuppressive M2 phenotype to the anticancer M1 phenotype [119]. In a different work, Meng *et al* created FePt@COP-FA nanocomposites (FPCF NCs), a multifunctional nanotherapeutic agent for the treatment of cancer. The nanocomposite's employment of FePt resulted in the death of ferroptosis-inducing cells as well as the accumulation of lipid peroxide. It has also been reported that tumor cells are reported to die under NIR due to the photothermal effect and that the immune system can be activated to stop the spread of metastatic cancers [130]. Together with the reports discussed above, studies have been carried out to develop different strategies (figure 2).

8. Combination of ferroptosis with chemodynamic therapy (CDT)

CDT is a newly developed cancer treatment method that involves using CDT chemicals to cause cell death by converting hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) into the most dangerous ROS, the hydroxyl radical ($\text{OH}\cdot$) [172]. Fe(III)-ART NPs have been used with CDT and ferroptosis cancer therapy in a study by Chen *et al*. Fe(III)-ART NPs have been demonstrated to be activated by intracellular GSH and catalyzed to produce free radicals, supporting long-term drug circulation. According to this research, ferroptosis, which is brought on by GSH depletion, supports CDT and has an anti-cancer effect. Additionally, the cascade reaction led to the

alkylation of biomolecules like protein, lipid, and DNA as well as the abundant production of free radicals that can kill cancer cells [141].

9. Combination of ferroptosis with sonodynamic therapy (SDT)

SDT is based on the accumulation of a sonosensitising chemical (sonosensitizer) in tumor tissues followed by activation of the drug by ultrasonic irradiation. Ultrasound's capacity to deeply penetrate tissues enables it to concentrate the substance responsible for activating the sonosensitizer on a localized region of the tumor [68]. With the development of combined therapies in the treatment of cancer, SDT has been used in many studies together with ferroptosis. Additionally, during SDT, a sonosensitizer generate ROS to kill cancer cells under ultrasound (US) source [173] (figure 2). For example, Xu *et al* used a manganese porphyrin-based MOF (Mn-MOF) as a nano-sensitizer to reduce GSH for ferroptosis along with enhanced SDT. Many *in vitro* and *in vivo* analyses such as ROS production, lipid peroxidation, O₂ production, GSH depletion, and antitumor efficacy have shown that upon US irradiation, it reduces GSH and GPX4, which facilitates the formation of ROS and ferroptosis to destroy cancer cells. It has been further suggested that the Mn-MOF used in the study increased the number of dendritic cells, and showed strong anti-tumor immunity with US irradiation, and improved immunosuppressive microenvironment [152].

10. Conclusion and future perspectives

The use of nanomaterials for cancer ferroptosis presents a promising avenue for future research and clinical applications. Nanomaterials have shown potential in inducing ferroptosis in cancer cells, offering a novel approach to cancer therapy. Recent progress in the development of nanomaterial based ferroptosis inducers has demonstrated their design, action mechanisms, and anticancer applications [10]. Furthermore, the future orientation for ferroptosis in cancer cells and the current unsettled issues have been deliberated, which may accelerate the clinical use of ferroptosis induction in cancer treatment [10]. For example, there is currently one Phase I clinical trial aiming to evaluate the safety, tolerability, pharmacokinetics profile and preliminary efficacy of intratumoral injection of carbon NP-loaded iron in patients with advanced solid tumors (NCT06048367). Tailoring nanomaterials to modulate ferroptosis in cancer therapy has attracted the attention of researchers, given the limited clinical applications of small-molecule ferroptosis inducers [174]. As the field progresses, we believe the number of clinical studies will increase which can eventually contribute towards their clinical translation.

The future of ferroptosis-based nanomaterials for cancer therapy is promising, as recent developments have shown multifunctional nanomaterials to be effective in inducing ferroptosis in cancer cells [175, 176]. However, challenges exist in the use of ferroptosis in cancer therapy, and future perspectives are essential to address these challenges and provide a basis for further research [177]. As discussed above, thanks to their physicochemical properties, nanomaterials can provide tremendous opportunities to achieve ferroptosis and cancer therapy through combinatorial approaches [178]. The effective physicochemical properties of nanomaterials, high targeting efficiency, high solubility and low side-effect potential have made it possible for them to stand out as therapeutic targets in cancer research. With the development of ferroptosis-based nanoinducers, endogenous iron deficiency can be reduced and the ferroptosis process of tumor cells can be induced by increasing the efficiency of the Fenton reaction.

Recent advances in ferroptosis-based self-assembled anti-cancer nanomaterials have emphasized their detailed mechanisms for inducing ferroptosis in tumor cells and their unique advantages [179]. Therefore, delineating the molecular mechanisms under the ferroptosis inducing nanomedicine studies is a must to pave the way for future challenges and opportunities. For example, the future of ferroptosis in cancer therapy also involve exploring the crosstalk between noncoding RNAs and ferroptosis, offering new opportunities for overcoming cancer progression [52, 180, 181]. Additionally, the role of noncoding RNAs and nanomaterials in mediating the ferroptosis process in tumor cells has been highlighted, indicating the potential for future research in this area [182]. Furthermore, the mechanism of ferroptosis and the involvement of circular RNAs in cancer regulation have been discussed, pointing towards future prospects and biological significance in cancer early diagnosis and precision therapy [183]. In conclusion, the future of using nanomaterials for cancer ferroptosis therapy holds great promise, with opportunities for further research and clinical applications. The development of novel nanomaterials and their targeted use in inducing ferroptosis in cancer cells presents a compelling avenue for future advancements in cancer therapy.

Data availability statement

No new data were created or analysed in this study.

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ORCID iD

Açelya Yilmazer <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2712-7450>

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